
WORK LIFE BALANCE INITIATIVES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The study aims to investigate which measures are in place in hospitality firms to promote a work-life balance, as well as how managers and employees, respectively, perceive its impact on performance. Accordingly, the study's objectives included learning more about the programs that hospitality companies have in place to help employees and managers, respectively, strike a balance between work and personal life, as well as how these initiatives affect employees' and managers' performance. The study used a qualitative research design, based on theoretical review of related literature. The theoretical basis was Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory of Motivation-Hygiene and Spill Over Theory. The results showed a favorable correlation between WLB programs and how employees are viewed in hospitality companies. The survey found that managers were generally supportive of WLB deployment as they hinted that because WLB benefits employees, it helps them perform better and better fulfill their responsibilities without experiencing stress or burnout. These programs (like sponsored leaves, work intervals, and flexible scheduling) were discovered to favorably impact the employee performance in terms of boosting productivity as they assist other employees to handle their responsibilities more effectively and stress-free. The investigation found that the hospitality employers can improve work-life balance by implementing a variety of HR practices, flexible work hours, paid maternity leave, compensated time off for child care.

Keywords: Work-life balance (WLB), WLB initiatives, Performance, Employee, Manager, Middle manager, Hospitality organizations.

INTRODUCTION

Every person is an essential component of society overall and families in particular. In today's business environment, employee performance plays a critical role in determining the attainment of organizational objectives. Consequently, companies seek various methods of inspiring their staff members to offer their utmost to the company. Every establishment has employee performance as a major concern. Every policy ought to be designed with improving worker performance in mind. Organizations must be able to monitor and enhance employee performance in order to stay at the top. If this doesn't happen, they can encounter a number of difficulties, which would be a setback for the company in the industry to which they belong.

Work-life balance (WLB) is gaining attention from management, staff, HR specialists, and wellness coordinators since it benefits both businesses and employees by promoting well-being and health, which in turn affects performance and efficiency (Bataneh, 2019). Performance in this context refers to how much an individual member of the organization contributes to the accomplishment of the organization's goals. It is evaluated based on the quantity and caliber of product produced, as well as on attendance, accommodating behavior, and timely delivery of work (Singh, 2018).

Cvenkel, (2021) asserts that the work-life balance (WLB) issue is increasingly urgent for businesses and employees, both at work and at home. Many workers find it difficult to reconcile their responsibilities to their families and their jobs because of the demanding nature of today's workplace. In this instance, work-life balance emerged as a prominent subject of study as a result of changing workplace dynamics brought on by economic uncertainty and an internal struggle for survival. The government and decision-makers place a high importance on work-life balance because they recognize that every individual is vital to the smooth functioning of society (Wong, et al., 2020). Because of the working population's increasing reliance on information technology, they are currently inundated with a larger volume of information. Workers must put in more hours and be available on the weekends. In addition, employees must always be reachable and swiftly respond to calls and emails after business hours. The pressure points at work have increased as a result (Sen & Hooja, 2018).

Due to this, there is growing concern that extended workdays, as well as more demands and obligations at work, are leaving less time for meaningful time spent with friends and family away from the office. Notably, a company's and an individual's positive approach to understanding the benefits of a happy and balanced work life as well as a life outside of the workplace leads to balance between work and life (Bataneh, 2019). A better work-life balance allows staff members to contribute more significantly to the growth and the prosperity of their firms when they work for businesses that place a high value on efficient and effective performance (Sen & Hooja, 2018).

Therefore, HR professionals look for ways to boost employee morale, maintain critical company knowledge, enhance their firms' bottom lines, and stay up to date with workplace innovations in today's fast-paced corporate environment (Gautam & Jain, 2018). WLB has become one of these techniques to positively impact employees because it has a significant impact on an individual's physical and mental development as well as the long-term viability of enterprises (Wong et al., 2020).

In view of this, companies in both the public and private sectors need to ensure that work-life balances are enhanced in order to ensure employee performance in an increasingly dynamic workplace. Globalization and technological innovation have made organizations more

competitive, which has forced them to give work-life balance initiatives top priority in an effort to boost employee performance—that is, the perception of employee performance.

Perceived performance of employees in this context is equal to actuality and potentiality, where actuality is the work that needs to be done on a daily basis and potentiality is the best job that can be done when all workplace limitations are eliminated and one believes it to be their potential resource. It's the extent to which a worker feels that something (like technology) can improve or worsen their ability to do their job. Accordingly, in the context of Work-Life Balance (WLB), perceived employee performance is the extent to which a worker believes that WLB activities would improve their performance. The perception is assessed by the individual using a variety of metrics, including efficacy, consistency, and efficiency (Singh, 2018). Human resource managers should incorporate as much as possible into the organization's aims and goals the welfare and well-being of the employees because their workforce is their most precious asset. This will help to maintain high employee performance and minimize work-life conflicts (Cvenkel, 2021). In light of this, it is imperative to investigate WLB and how it affects workers' performance.

The goal of the work life quality and the goal of life management is to foster an environment of liberty, autonomy, and involvement in which employees collaborate to a shared goal and subjective metrics (Susan & Jayan, 2013). The late 1960s saw the start of measuring and evaluating the quality of working life, which was centered on the interaction between the employee and the workplace and related to specific aspects of working.

Quality of life at work (QWL) has been implemented by companies as a strategy to enhance workers' productivity, performance, and competitiveness while lowering employee turnover and absenteeism without increasing management costs (Amah, 2016). It also increases employee satisfaction and pride, as well as affective commitment and worker integration into the organization (Zhao et al. 2013, Quick et al. 2013). Work Quality Life can be described in terms of an employee's job happiness, work-related behaviors, reward, job security, social activities, and work-family balance (Bagtasos, 2011,; Kanten & Sadulhah, 2012). The opportunity to participate in communal affairs and activities, while still in a gainful employment.

To provide companies with a more comprehensive understanding of the aspects influencing the work experience, the notion of "work-related quality of life" was developed. In addition to working circumstances, it also includes larger non-work elements like general life happiness and the work-home interface that have an impact on an employee's relationship with their work (Alfonso et al, 2016).

"A process by which an organization responds to employee needs by developing mechanisms to allow them to fully share in making the decisions that design their lives at work" is how Robbins (1989) described QWL; various people have varied definitions of what a quality work life is. Many phrases have been used to refer to implemented quality of working life programs, such as "Work improvement," "Job enrichment," "Worker's participation," and "Industrial democracy" (Teryimaetal, 2016). In a nutshell, QWL and WLB can be used interchangeably, to mean and apply to the same concept.

Lau and Bruce (1998) state that QWL is a dynamic, multifaceted construct that presently encompasses ideas like reward structures, participation in decision-making, training and career growth chances, and job stability. According to Wyatt and Wah (2001), a work atmosphere where employees' activities are valued is necessary for QWL. It means that work is structured in a way that reduces boredom and increases variation and adaptability for

employees through the adoption of policies and methods, which the employee is part and parcel of. Such remains a panacea for employees maximal performance.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Furthermore, research indicates that most employees prioritize work-life balance (WLB) initiatives over pay, according to Cvenkel (2021). More than half of respondents in a 2016 Scott study of 2000 employees in the UK stated that they choose jobs that encourage work-life balance over ones that offer alluring compensation and benefits. Nonetheless, despite their importance, there hasn't been much research done on how work-life balance (WLB) efforts affect employees' performance in hospitality firms. For instance, Wong et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis to investigate the correlation between WLB arrangements and organizational performance; Chandran and Abukhalifeh (2021) conducted a systematic literature review of research on WLB in the hospitality sector since the year 2000; Gautam and Jain (2018) studied the challenges and solutions of WLB; and Roopavathi and Kishore (2021) studied the effect of WLB on employee performance. Nevertheless, none of these studies have particularly examined how WLB initiatives affect workers' performance in hospitality firms from the viewpoints of managers and employees. The fact that workers are placing a higher priority on WLB poses a challenge for the hospitality sector, as no research has explicitly looked at how WLB initiatives affect how managers and staff in these types of organizations perceive their employees' performance. Consequently, this study aims to fill the research gap by investigating how WLB efforts affect employees' perceptions of their performance in hospitality firms from the combined perspectives of managers and employees.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Work-life balance (WLB) is the capacity to maintain a sense of control, to be competitive and productive at work, and to conduct a happy, healthy work life with adequate free time. It involves developing awareness and focus in the face of competing activities and tasks that seem to go on forever. It increases worker motivation, minimizes stress, and promotes production. An employee can lead a high-quality work life and have a great work-life balance.

Figure 2.1 Work Life Balance Relationship with Employee Performance (Obiageli, et al., 2015)

2.2 WORK LIFE BALANCE

Policies that were once referred to as "family-friendly" but are now understood to encompass more than just the family unit are now referred to as "work-life balance." The term "work-life balance" describes flexible working arrangements that enable a balance between professional and personal duties for both parents and non-parents (Redmond, et al., 2006).

Work-life conflict that employees encounter is where work-life balance methods first emerged. Inter-role conflict known as "work-life conflict" arises when an individual's responsibilities as an employee collide with those of a spouse, parent, or participant in other extracurricular or religious activities. The idea of work-life conflict acknowledges that most people play several roles in their lives. Work-life balance techniques assist reduce work-life conflict while addressing its causes as well (Lero and Bardoel, 2007). Work-life conflicts can have a number of causes, including excessive workloads and demanding jobs.

After a thorough analysis of the work-life literature, it is possible to classify Work Life Balance initiatives into four main categories: flexible work arrangements (such as working from home or compressed hours); leave arrangements (such as annual leave or parental leave); dependent care assistance (such as child care arrangements and crèches); and general services (such as employment assistant programs) (Obiageli, et al., 2015; De Cieri and Bardoel, 2009). Work-life policies, also known as family-friendly or family-responsive policies, are practices designed to assist employees in managing their workload and downtime. They are also referred to in the literature as work-family policies. The phrase "work-life balance" has supplanted the previous one, "work-family balance," in recent years (Hudson Resourcing, 2005). In addition to employment, there are other life activities that must be balanced, such as education, travel, sports, volunteer work, personal growth, leisure, and elder care. A person who finds a suitable level of participation or "fit" between the various responsibilities in their life is said to have a work-life balance.

In order to preserve a general sense of harmony in one's life, Clarke, et al., (2004) state that work-life balance is typically connected with equilibrium between the time and effort one invests to work and personal activities. Understanding the many demands placed on us and the personal resources—our time and energy—that we might use to meet those demands is crucial to understanding work-life balance. Studies have demonstrated that employees with some degree of control over their work environment are less likely to experience health problems connected to stress. These findings have significant implications for the notion of work-life balance. Work-life balance programs can be implemented by organizations to help employees better balance work and family obligations, enhance their own well-being, and benefit the organization as a whole. Family-friendly policies come in a wide range and include, but are not limited to, the following: Flexible work schedules, job sharing, part-time employment, shortened workweeks, telecommuting, on-site child care according to Hartel, (2007), cited in Obiageli, et al., (2015).

Although work-life balance studies have made major contributions to our understanding of the phenomenon, there is still a considerable deal of unevenness in these research when conducted in non- Western contexts. In summary, a great deal of study has been done on work-life balance in the West, but far less has been done to examine the idea of work-life balance for persons in Nigeria (Ojo, et al., 2014).

2.2.1 Self Rostering

Workers self-roster their own schedules whenever it suits them. The organization allows its employees to set their own schedules and decides each day how many workers and what skills are needed. Employees can more easily divide their time between work and play as a result.

2.2.2 Flexible of Teleworking

Employees truly cherish the flexible scheduling option of teleworking, or working from home, and its popularity is rising, according to Wong et al. (2020). Modern communication

tools enable workers to perform their tasks at a distance. They can often work from satellite offices or local telecenters, or from their homes. Workers are free to attend to personal or non-work-related problems as long as it doesn't negatively impact output or quality (Obiageli, et al., 2015).

Thanks to increasingly more sophisticated and affordable technology, employees can now work remotely utilizing a range of devices, including PCs, cell phones, and email. With the help of these gadgets, workers can continue to do their duties even when they are not at their offices. Workers who are not formally "on the job" might respond to emails or voicemails on the weekends or after hours (Roopavathi & Kishore, 2021). Scholars have found that workers who feel that their jobs are an integral part of who they are will be more willing to use these communication technologies to work in their leisure activities domains. Even if teleworking isn't practical or suitable for every profession (such as the majority of positions in the hotel industry), it does help employees save a lot of money, time, and worry when it comes to commuting. Furthermore, it ensures that workers have a healthy work-life balance and provides time for workplace collaboration upon arrival (Wong et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Welfare Policy

Again, assistance with child care can boost employee motivation and productivity. It also reduces accidents, turnover, and absenteeism. Work-life balance and job satisfaction can both be significantly impacted by the availability of childcare for working parents. As it is currently too costly for a potential wage worker to stay at home, families with two earners are more prevalent. The option of having a caregiver who stays at home is no longer available to families. Child care options are therefore becoming more and more necessary in order to help workers balance their personal and professional lives. There are several options for child care, including host parent care, teen care, day care centers, crèches, and leader-at-home programs (Chandran & Abukhalifeh, 2021).

2.2.4 Flexible Work shifts

Additionally, with flexible scheduling, employees are given the freedom to decide when to start and stop their workday if a certain number of hours are worked. They are competent to handle emergencies and personal or family responsibilities as a result. A flexible schedule gives workers more options, which is particularly helpful for jobs where exact work hours aren't that critical. Further work-life balance policies that lead to happier and more productive staff members include company-sponsored educational initiatives, like those on the well-being of a new child or family, which have been associated with a decline in work-life conflicts (Garg & Yajurvedi, 2016).

2.2.5 Leave Policy

The number of hours or days that employees of a company are allowed to take off from work in a given period of time without facing repercussions is known as leave. The employer pays for this time off, which employees can seek for whatever reason they would like to take a break from work. Additionally, it enables workers to decompress from work-related stress and strike a balance between work and personal obligations. This kind of work-life balance promotes a balance between work and personal interests by enabling employees to carry out additional responsibilities outside of the workplace. There are various kinds of leave policies, including:

annual leave, parental leave, carer's leave, paid family leave, sick leave and study leave. Also, compassionate leave is available for a bereaved employee.

2.3 EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

One of the most crucial aspects of the workplace is employee performance in a company. It can assist the company in making better use of and increases the capacity of its human resources. It translates into effective communication and service delivery, which benefits every department inside the company. In order to accomplish this, the firm must implement policies that will motivate worker performance. An employee's skill, effort, and opportunity all play a part in how well they succeed at work. However, measurements may be made in terms of the products or outcomes (Ferris et al., 1998). According to Bernaddin and Russell (1998) and Iigenand Schneider, (1991), referred in Obiageli, et al., (2015) performance is the record of results achieved on a given job function or activity during a given time period. This definition sees performance as a collection of results generated over a specific amount of time. For research purposes, the researchers have therefore defined employee performance as "achievement of targets of the tasks assigned to employees within particular period of time." Performance includes judgment and assessment processes in addition to the action itself.

Campbell (1993), cited in Obiageli, et al., (2015) asserts that an employee's success is determined by how well they carry out their assigned responsibilities and by their observable, quantifiable actions. For an organization to succeed and gain a competitive edge, its workforce must perform at a high level (Frese, 2002, cited in Obiageli, et al., 2015). The business lexicon defines employee performance as the tasks associated with a worker's job that are required of them and the quality of those tasks' execution. The performance of employees determines the success of the organization. As a result, it's critical for managers to have a comprehensive strategy for leading and developing their staff. The primary goal of the hospitality industry, which are in the service sector, is client satisfaction. Employee performance and the services they provide to customers are linked. Employees go above and beyond the call of duty when they deliver exceptional customer service. The degree of customer service that a business provides determines how well-liked its services are. The performance of their employees is nearly the only factor that determines business for the service industry. For this reason, management needs to explore for several approaches to raise employee performance.

2.3.1 Service Delivery

According to Lovelock and Wirtz, (2004), service delivery describes "where," "when," and "how" the service product is supplied to the client. According to Danaher and Mattsson (1994), the service delivery process can be divided into service encounters, which make up the majority of the entire process. Additionally, managers may need to make some generalizations within service types for various services and service providers, as mentioned by Chowdhary and Prakash (2007), to take this into account when designing it. Accordingly, the ability to provide the highest possible quality of services will give service companies a competitive edge over other businesses in the same sector (Turel, et al., 2007). Work-life balance, according to Lasch (1999), improves employee service delivery.

The term "service delivery" refers to the part of business that describes the exchange of information or tasks between service providers and clients.

Employees are tasked with providing the services, and their performance is very important. This is due to the fact that it impacts a variety of factors, including customer happiness, attracting and keeping new clients, managing complaints, hitting goals, sales turnover, profitability, market shares, and the company's reputation. Employee performance matters in a variety of service industries, not just hospitality industry. Improved performance results in

customers being satisfied. Services must be rendered with the least amount of processing and waiting time, appropriate response, promptness, and the ability to serve a large number of clients when demand warrants.

The manager do things right, command, control and seek stability and predictable and therefore efficient; while the leader do the right things, inspire, empower, seek flexibility and change and is very effective (Amah, 2016). Both are attributes of employee performance, motivation and satisfaction.

2.4 WORK LIFE BALANCE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Liu et al. (2021) state that businesses can invest in work-life balance (WLB) programs and policies to boost employee productivity, enhance customer service, lower absenteeism, lower stress levels among staff, improve employees' health and wellbeing, boost commitment, loyalty, and motivation, and have a happier, more motivated workforce. Work-life balance is therefore essential for employees and increases their productivity inside the organization (Liu et al., 2021). Many researches have been conducted to look into the relationship between WLB programs and workers' productivity, and the results have shown that the two are positively correlated. For instance, Hughes and Bozionelos (2015) set out to look into the perspectives of male workers in an industry where men are disproportionately represented when it comes to work-life balance-related issues. It became evident that work-life imbalance was the main reason for participants' dissatisfaction, which was more than just a cause for alarm. Furthermore, participants made a clear connection between withdrawal habits and problems with work-life balance, including turnover and phony sick leaves.

Roopavathi and Kishore (2021) looked into the impact of work-life balance on workers' output. The study aimed to comprehensively examine the possible connections between labor flexibility and production efficiency, relationships between employer-employee relationships and increased productivity, work environment and employee turnover rate, and, lastly, job protection and employee retention. The study came to the conclusion that job protection, employer-employee connections, labor stability, and a positive work environment all had a beneficial impact on improved production quality, increased efficiency, a lower turnover rate, and staff retention. The results showed that workers have negative reactions to a believe there is a work-life imbalance and that, in order to boost employee performance, CEOs should implement WLB programs.

Khatri and Behl (2013) conducted a study to look at how WLB affected workers' productivity in companies. They attempted to look at the definition of work-life balance in the context of employment relations, as well as what it meant for employers and employees. The sample consisted of 200 regular employees from the different HDFC Bank, Bajaj Alliance, and Punjab National Bank offices in Jammu City, J&K State. A Likert scale was used to gather data. ANOVA, regression, factor analysis, and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. The findings showed that the WLB method is appropriate in situations where employers and workers work together and that it has a positive correlation with employees' success within the organization.

Adikaram and Jayatilake (2016) evaluated the effect of WLB on workers' job satisfaction at private commercial banks in Sri Lanka in a 2016 study. WLB and job satisfaction in connection to working conditions, working hours, WLB initiatives, employee intention to change employment, and work pressure were the variables taken into consideration. Both primary and secondary sources were used to obtain the data. A total of 150 surveys were distributed to employees of different commercial banks. A Likert scale was employed to collect the data. Regression analysis and correlation were used to examine the data. The

findings showed that work-life balance has a major impact on employee job satisfaction in Sri Lanka's private sector commercial banks.

Cvenkel (2021) looked at managerial and non-managerial employees' perceptions on WLB in an effort to encourage a more emotionally sound workplace. The study specifically examined work-family conflicts, health and well-being, WLB contentment initiatives, and the firm's WLB (also known as family-friendly policies) implementation. 36 semi-structured interviews and two focus groups were used in the study's qualitative methodological approach to collect data from management and non-managerial staff members of a variety of occupational groups. The study found that work-life conflicts that affect employees' WLB include stress at work, drug usage, bad relationships, resource scarcity, and other external factors. Organizational family-friendly work-life balance (WLB) programs that prioritize fun and family-friendly activities, counseling, privacy, trust, and regular breaks have been shown to enhance employee health and well-being, and consequently, their performance at work. Examples of workers in an organization of health and well-being efforts that support WLB satisfaction: flexible work schedules, gym membership, employer-sponsored health insurance, wellness programs, employee assistance programs (EAPs), and equity at work.

2.5 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study's main objective is to determine how WLB efforts impact workers' performance in hospitality organizations as reported by managers and staff in the industry. As said earlier, this attempts to offer a review of past scholarly studies that looked at theories regarding the connection between workers' performance and WLB activities. The following is a review of a theory and scholarly works regarding the relationship between WLB efforts and workers' performance.

2.5.1 HERZBERG'S TWO-FACTOR THEORY OF MOTIVATION-HYGIENE

In 1959, Herzberg developed a model that included two categories of the elements influencing people's perceptions about their jobs: motivators and hygiene considerations. He concluded that factors such as status, income, working conditions, supervision, personal life, interpersonal connections, safety, and company policy are more sanitary than motivating, (Herzberg, 2015). This hypothesis postulates that while the absence of sanitary variables may lead to employee dissatisfaction, their presence may also encourage or boost it. However, he came to the conclusion that the components of a person's work that enhanced it were the motivators; specifically, he identified five variables—advancement, responsibility, the task itself, achievement, and recognition—that were critical markers of job satisfaction. While the hygiene criteria (dissatisfiers) usually only resulted in transient changes in work mindsets and performance that quickly returned to their former level, and these motivators (satisfiers) were linked to long-term favorable effects on job outcomes (Haque, et al., 2014). In a nutshell, job satisfaction describes how someone feels about their work, which is often connected to the duties they are given. Dissatisfiers, on the other hand, are associated with an individual's perception of their workplace environment. A person is satisfied with what they accomplish, yet dissatisfied with the circumstances around their activities (Herzberg, 2015).

In this instance, the implementation—or lack thereof—of WLB initiatives will be based on the hygiene elements and motivators and how their presence or absence affects employees in the hospitality businesses.

2.5.2 SPILL OVER THEORY

This research is based on Guest's (2002) spillover theory. It makes assumptions about the circumstances that lead to spillover between the family microsystem and the work

microsystem. It could be advantageous or detrimental. Work-family relationships that are inflexibly scheduled in terms of both space and time will have a detrimental impact on behavior, energy, and time management. Positive spillover is facilitated by flexibility, which allows people to integrate and overlap work and home duties in terms of time and space. This is crucial for attaining a healthy work-life balance. The contexts of work and home are where the factors affecting work-life balance are found, according to Guest (2002). Workplace expectations, work culture, and home demands are examples of contextual determinants. Individual variables include gender and age, life and career stage, work orientation (i.e., the degree to which work (or home) is a key life focus), personality, energy, and personal control and coping. The study's factors fall within the categories of contextual determinants, which also include service delivery and leave policy. The requirement of work is service delivery, but the leave policy represents the work culture.

There have been both objective and subjective definitions of what work-life balance is. Work and uncommitted or leisure time hours outside of work are included in the objective metrics. States of imbalance and equilibrium are referred to as subjective indicators. Additionally, balance can be reported when job and home are given equal weight or when one chooses to prioritize one over the other. When one area of life interferes with another, spillover happens. Several other benefits of work-life balance include one's own performance at work and at home, effect on coworkers, family, and friends, and overall well-being and pleasure at work, home, and in life.

This theory is relevant to the study because it states that companies should implement work-life policies that allow employees to have a good work-life balance, which will increase their commitment to the organization's objectives.

3.0 DISCUSSION

According to Ojo's (2012) opinion, every individual is involved in issues that need them to prioritize their professional role and personal devotion. Additionally, it was discovered that although the hospitality industry has leave policies in place, they still need to be improved. The results of this study showed that leave policies and service delivery had a very high favorable correlation. An effective leave policy also encourages employees to perform their jobs more effectively. For an employee to remain productive in the organization, the organization must continue to improve on their work life balance incentives. This will produce an employee that will be more effective and efficient in delivery of services to the customer. This study has shown that work life balance is an important factor that brings about employee performance. The employee is productive by his ability to render a "come back again services" to their customer and this is achieved when employee are motivated by the various leave policy given to them by the organization.

4.0 CONCLUSION

According to the findings of Rubel and Kee's (2014) study, job satisfaction has an impact on employees' performance and the effectiveness of the business. As a result, a high-quality workplace is one in which employees are seen as the primary part of the business, they face intellectual challenges, the workplace promotes the success and personal potential of its members, and everything is executed flawlessly.

The study comes to the conclusion that a business can really benefit from a work-life balance concept. This is due to the fact that each employee's social and psychological well-being must be appropriately managed if they are to be considered an asset to the company rather than merely a tool for carrying out daily tasks.

According to Vanscotter (2000) cited in Obiageli, et al., (2015), an organization's excellent employee performance creates more opportunities for its workers than low performance does. Employers must so seek out more effective strategies for raising worker performance through engagement. Assisting them in setting priorities for their life and work activities will accomplish this. When this is accomplished, the worker is inspired to provide their services in an effective and efficient manner. Evidences abound that service organizations yield fully and achieve productive results from the employees with QWL.

When workers can manage the demands of their professional and personal lives, they are happy. Additionally, management and staff relationships have improved. Support from management for workers' work-life balance cultivates positive working relationships with management, which enhances efficient communication inside the company.

Numerous academics concurred with the conclusion that employee performance and work-life balance are positively correlated.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Consequent upon this theoretical review and arising from the findings, the following recommendations emanate:

1. The management of the hospitality industry should make sure that they employ a variety of work-life incentives to encourage employees to give their best work.
2. Provision of family welfare policies to encourage care for dependent.
3. Managers of these organisations should create activities that improve employee leisure time. Sport activities.
4. Additionally, supervisors in these establishments ought to motivate their staff members to schedule their leaves at a time that works for them after completing all work-related tasks.
5. The hospitality industry management should ensure that they use various work-life incentives that motivate staff members to perform better at work.
6. As one of the WLB strategies, hospitality firms must invest in technological innovation in order to eliminate the need for paper documents and human labor.
7. Based on the results from this study, hospitality firms should develop a work-life balance strategy for each job role inside the company. This will help to boost employee productivity and job satisfaction. As a result, companies ought to implement this tactic to improve worker performance.
8. Workshops and seminars on time management, stress reduction, effective job management, and prioritizing employees' duties should be arranged by hospitality firms. Employees who receive time management and stress management training at work will develop the habit of being punctual, which will improve their WLB and performance.

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